

**THE LEXICAL SEMANTIC PECULARITIES OF ECOLOGICAL TERMS
IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES**

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Annotation: this article thesis deals with the Lexical Semantic Peculiarities of ecological terms both Languages (English and Uzbek). Although the relationship between linguistics and ecology has only recently been established, the formation of ecology as a science has been largely reflected in lexicographic sources, such as dictionaries. This can be seen in the example of Russian and English.

Key words: semantic meaning ,lexical terms, ecology, terminology, Uzbek, English languages.

Аннотация: диссертация посвящена лексико-семантическим особенностям экологических терминов.

на обоих языках (английском и узбекском). Хотя связь между лингвистикой и экологией была установлена только недавно, формирование экологии как науки в значительной степени отражено в лексикографических источниках, таких как словари. Это видно на примере русского и английского языков.

Introduction. Ecological terminology is to collect the terms of ecological science, to define their lexical-semantic groups, their paradigmatic relations and composition, to determine the place of the international ecoterm and thermoelements in the layers, and to develop recommendations for the regulation of ecological terms. According to their lexical-semantic, derivative, paradigmatic structures and forms.

The main directions of eco linguistics and subsequent development of Uzbek linguistics are defined;

Lexical-semantic paradigms of ecological terms in the Uzbek language have been identified; Synonymic, hyper-hyponimic, partonimic, graduonimic and antonymic relationships in ecological terms are identified;

Types of ecological terminology according to their forms have been identified and their functional-methodological features are compared;

The role of international terminology and thermoelements in the system of ecological terminology has been shown;

Specific proposals have been developed on the regulation of ecological terminology and their proper usage in the Uzbek language in various forms;

Proportionality of the processes related to the formation and development of the ecological terminology system with the ecological consciousness, ecological

awareness and ecological culture of the population is mentioned
Implementation of the research results. Based on the study of ecological terminology in Uzbek: words and terms such as ecological linguistics, ecological crisis, ecological taxonomy, ecological pyramid, ecogarden, ecomarket, ecological product, chemical pollution, desertification, water erosion, wind erosion, side erosion;

environmental disaster - environmental hazard - ecological disaster - ecological crisis, ecological taxonomy - ecological angle, hypoxia - air deficiency, mud - mantle, earth crust - pedosphere, soil generation - soil formation, gumid - watery, arid - drought, white acid - Talas parpi, blooming grass, Fergana tulips - tulips, Grace tulip - red tulips, beautifully forming - formovka, the explanations of such kind of terms, scientific assumptions of the dissertation were used in the activities of Committee on the Issues of Ecology and Environment Protection of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the deputy group of the Ecological Movement. Also, the results of the research and the scientific conclusions of the dissertation were the source of the preparation of the "Concept for the Development of

Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan". As a result, the Committee on the Issues of Ecology and Environment Protection and the Ecological Movement of Uzbekistan held a series of talks, lectures and speeches organized by the local people, such as, "Онажоним табиат" (Mother Nature),

- The explanation of terms such as ecological crisis, ecological situation, ecological taxonomy, ecotourism, ecological product, ozone layer, and the results

of the research were used for the preparation of the "Mezon" program broadcast on National Television and Radio Company's channel "Madaniyat va ma'rifat". The program on environmental problems analysis, ecological awareness, ecological knowledge and ecological culture of the population was prepared on the basis of

the article materials. (Reference number 02-16 / 386 of the State unitary enterprise "Madaniyat va ma'rifat" channel of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan on August);

- The dissertation includes the explanations of the plants, such as "zarhallangan kiyikpanja, uchqat, bolquray, sug'ur o't, omonqora, marmarak, tillarang sug'uro't, tulkiqyruq, tuyaqorin, isiriq, oq jusan, qo'ng'irbosh, eshakmiya, shirinmiya, devpechak, qizilkandir, chakanda, zog'oza, toron, sachratqi, shotara, bobuna, itburun, choyo't, quyonsuyak, sanchiqo't, kovrak, savrinjon, bo'znoch, ermon" which are included in the "Red Book", and (A-7-21) conclusions about the functional-methodological and semantic features of terms, such as dendroflora, greenhouse, nursery, hybrid plant, nursery, plant genetic fund, selection, climatization, microclonal reproduction of plants, phytogerman, vaccinated plant, herbal form related to their protection. It was used in the light of the project dedicated to the theme "Transformative assessment of vegetation cover on the northern part of the Fergana valley" (reference № 89.03.2852 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 14, 2018). As a result, the project's scientific value has increased and interdisciplinary integration has been achieved.

Literature review.

G.S. Rosenberg's analysis of the definition of the term "ecology" reveals two main trends in the interpretation of ecology. That is, the first as a biological network, and

the second as a science that studies man and his activities. In this case, the author writes, it is appropriate to call the basic definitions of the classical term

"bioecology" and "socioecology" the most outdated concepts. British scientists have made significant contributions to the development of environmental science and terminology. Suffice it to say that the scientific work of the English naturalist Charles Darwin was a catalyst for the development of ecological ideas. The English scientist T. Spencer, in his 1870 study of Sociology, laid the foundations of human ecology. One of the central concepts of ecological science is the concept of ecosystem, introduced in 1935 by researcher Arthur Tensley.

Ye.A. Vistorobes analyzes the basic conceptual semantic aspect of the ecological term system in 3 microns. 1). Analytical ecology, 2). Global ecology 3). Historical and dynamic ecology. It is this micro-area that forms the basis of the system of ecological terms. Active research in the field of ecology allows to identify new knowledge and data. Now ecology has become a comprehensive field of science that belongs not only to nature but also to society. At present, human knowledge and socio-economic development cannot be developed without taking into account environmental laws. In addition, the analysis of ecological concepts, which are part of the knowledge of ecological phenomena and find their material expression through the concepts of functionally defined terms, shows that the ecological principle of a new dynamic period in human history has been formed. This can be explained by the fact that environmental knowledge is constantly increasing in response to a variety of human activities. For objective reasons, N.N. In Kryuchkova's words, they are being ecologized. Lexical-semantic groups of Uzbek

and English ecology, samples of ecological nominations are an integral part of the vocabulary of these languages. There is already a need to compile (present) them in the form of a monolingual dictionary or 2-3 language translation dictionaries and to create such ecological lexical sources. This requires a comprehensive linguistic analysis of the ecological lexicon, the identification of its components, models and methods of construction, the study and classification of lexical semantic features.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Джурабаева З. Сув билан боғлиқ экология терминлари // АДУ «Илмий хабарнома»си. – Андижон, 2011. –№4. –Б. 82-84. (10.00.00. №11)
2. Majidova M. Эколингвистика фани ҳақида // Til va adabiyot ta’limi. –Тошкент, 2011. –№9. –Б. 54-57. (10.00.00. №9)
3. Sadikov N. Туркий тилларнинг экологик лексикаси ҳақида // Filologiya masalalari. – Baki: Elm va tahsil, 2012. –№5. –Б. 122-127. (10.00.00. №7)
4. Azizova Z. Ekologik ta’limda semik usuldan foydalanish // Til va adabiyot ta’limi. –Тошкент, 2012. –№10. –Б. 34-36. (10.00.00. №9)
5. Karimov M. Эколингвистиканинг долзарб муаммолари // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. –Тошкент, 2012. –№1. –Б. 43-47. (10.00.00. №14)
6. To'rayeva Sh. Sodda ko‘rinishdagi ekologiya terminlari va ularning til xususiyatlari // Til va adabiyot ta’limi. –Тошкент, 2013. –№9. –Б. 38-40.
7. Снакин. В.В. Экология и охрана природы. Словарь справочник. Под.ред.академика А.Л. Яншина. – М.: Academia.- 2018. -387с
8. Dodson S.I. et al. Ecology. - New York: Oxford University Press, 2013. - 464 p. - URL: <http://www.questia.com>